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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Katta guruh tarbiyalanuvchilarida kasb haqidagi dastlabki tasavvurlarni shakllantirish metodikasini innovatsion ekotizim sharoitida takomillashtirish	18
Uralova Fotima Baxtiyor qizi	
Malakali sportchilarning kommunikativ qobiliyatlarini takomillashtirishda sotsiologik yondashuv (gandbolchilar misolida).....	23
G. A. Valiyeva	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida motor alaiyal bolalarni ruhiy va nutqiy rivojlantirish usullari	27
Suyunova Surayyo Ulash qizi	
Sog'lom bola ekotizimining asoslari: ovqatlanish, immunitet va rivojlanish	31
Israilova Xusnida Adilovna	
Mobil ilovalar yordamida mustaqil o'qishni rivojlantirish	37
Raximova Feruza Najmiddinovna	
Biologiya darslarida muammoli ta'lim texnologiyasini qo'llash orqali mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish	42
Dauekeeva Gulistan Orinbaevna	
Talabalarga ingliz tilidagi matnlarni kommunikativ metod yordamida o'qish texnikasini takomillashtirish usullari	46
Mo'minova Mahliyo Axrorjonovna	
Velosiped haydashning afzalliklari.....	49
Raxmonova Go'zal Bobir qizi	
Компетентностный подход как стратегическая основа модернизации образования и его реализация в преподавании русского языка как иностранного в Узбекистане	54
Мирзакбарова Севда Вахиддиновна	
Umumta'lim maktablarida texnologiya fani mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari va metodlari.....	58
Ziyamova Gulbaxor Tulabayevna	
Типы аббревиации в русском и узбекском языках: сравнительно-типологический анализ.....	62
Рахмонова Бахтигул Пайзилловна	
Maktabgacha ta'limda nutqni rivojlantirish jarayonida didaktik o'yinlardan foydalanish metodikasi	65
Abidjonova Mushtariybonu Qobiljon qizi	
Tarbiyaviy tadbirlarni samarali tashkil etishda maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti va ota-onalarning o'zaro hamkorlik masalalari.....	71
Sanayeva Surayyo Bobonazarovna, Jabborova Shaxina G'affor qizi	
Qadriyatli yondashuv asosida talabalarni ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalash mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish ..	76
G'aybullayev Quvonchbek G'olibovich	
Maktab o'quvchilarida stressga barqarorlik namoyon bo'lishining psixologik tahlili	83
Ismoilova N. Z.	
Yoshlar ma'naviyatini shakllantirishda milliy qadriyatlarning o'rni.....	87
Karshiyev Jaxongir Abdirayimovich	
Funksional savodxonlikni rivojlantirishda o'qish savodxonligining o'rni va ahamiyati	91
Xatamova Munisa Mamadulla qizi	
Transformatsiyalash tizimi asosida o'quvchilarning loyihalash kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish samaradorligi	95
Jurayeva Zulayxo Islomovna	
Zamonaviy boshqaruv nazariyalarida rahbar muloqoti (transformatsion, kommunikativ va ishtirokchi boshqaruv yondashuvlari asosida).....	102
Islamova Difuza Dilshodovna	

Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida pedagogik kompetentlikni tabaqalashgan yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish mazmuni	107
Begmatova Nasiba Mengnarovna	
Bo'lajak maxsus pedagoglarni inklyuziv ta'limda subyektlar faoliyatini o'rgatish metodikasi	112
Dilshodov Abrorjon Dilshodjon o'g'li	
Pre-Reading Activities to Enhance Foreign Language Reading Comprehension: Reading "The Adventures of Tom Sawyer" in 10–11 Grades	118
Djumaniyazova Zulfiya Kaliyevna	
Nutq aktlarini o'rgatishda autentik materiallardan foydalanishning metodik imkoniyatlari (filologik yo'nalish talabalari misolida)	122
Fayzulloeva Chevar G'ayrat qizi	
Yangi O'zbekistonda talaba-yoshlarni milliy yuksaltirishda jadid-marifatparvarlari ilgari surgan g'oyalarning o'rni va roli	125
Mamadaliyev Abduvoxid Maxsitaliyevich	
Gimnastikaning O'zbekistonga kirib kelish va rivojlanish tarixi	128
N. Q. Mamasidova	
Uglevodorodlar tarkibini aniqlashda massa ulushiga asoslangan reflektiv yondashuv (7-9-sinflar misolida)	131
Maxamadiyev Sharofiddin Jumaboyevich, Smanova Zulayxo Asanalievna	
Screencasting materiallarini yaratish va ularni o'quv jarayonida qo'llash	134
Maxmudova Dilfuza Meliyevna, Ergashov Niyozxon Ilyozxon o'g'li	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda so'z shakllanishini psixolingvistik asoslari	137
Moxirabonu G'aniyeva Adxam qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'limdagi muammolar va yechimlar: o'zbekiston respublikasi tajribasi	140
N. Sh. Miryusupova	
Interaktiv kartografik resurslar va ularning ta'lim jarayonida qo'llanilishining didaktik, kognitiv hamda metodik asoslari	143
Olimova Aziza Abdullayevna	
Mentorlik tizimining tarixiy ildizlari va rivojlanish bosqichlari	147
Oxunova Dilnoza Qaxxorjonovna, Abdumannonova Durdonaxon Shuxratjon qizi	
Talabalarning psixologik holati va stress omillarining prokrastinatsiyaga ta'siri hamda mustaqil ta'lim faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash usullari	150
Razakov Farxod Kuvondikovich, Rajabov Hikmat Toshevich	
Talabalarni stulda o'tirgan qiyofachi portreti ranglavhasini ishlashga o'rgatish metodikasi	154
Sadatov Chori Xolmuradovich	
Organik kimyo fanini o'qitishda teskari ta'lim va texnologiyalarning ahamiyati	158
Umrbekova Maftuna Ulug'bek qizi, Babanazarova Ayzada Omirbaevna, Abdulkakimova Gulziyba Ziyatdinovna	
Duduqlanishni bartaraf etishda kompleks metodlarini qo'llashning samaradorligi	162
Xasanova Barnoxon Abdusattor qizi	
Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning pedagogik kompetentligini takomillashtirish	165
Xolbozorova Nasiba Xolbozar qizi	
Проектирование персонализированных образовательных сценариев в дошкольном образовании средствами генеративного искусственного интеллекта	168
Пак Диана Александровна	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarni tayyorlashda STEAM yondashuvining roli	170
Atenov Jandarbek Dayrabay o'g'li	
Innovatsion ta'lim muhitida talabalarning kasbiy muloqot kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	173
Bo'ltakov Sanjarbek Xazratqul o'g'li	
Alohida ta'lim ehtiyojlari mavjud bo'lgan bolalar uchun inklyuziv ta'lim tizimining ahamiyati	176
Mehmonova Nodiraxon Yusufxon qizi	

Duduqlanish nutq kamchiligini korreksiyalashning maxsus va integratsiyalashgan texnologiyalarini rivojlantirish.....	180
Boxodirova Gulasaxon Ibrohimovna	
Эссе как инструмент формирования и диагностики компетенций в системе высшего образования .	184
Шейхмамбетов Сервер Рефикович	
Matallar va folklor hikoyalari: maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida interaktiv dars texnologiyalari.....	188
Azimova Nodira Hikmatovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirish va ularni sportga yo'naltirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	191
Norboyev Komiljon Jurakulovich, Rustamova Kamola Xayrulla qizi	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlarning o'qitilishining ahamiyati.....	194
Burkhanova Sabo Tulanovna	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida O'zbekistonning eng yangi tarixini o'qitishning metodologik asoslari va muammolari	197
Norbutayeva Guzal Abdig'ofurovna	
Ta'lim tashkilotlarida sifadni boshqarish jarayonlarini tizimli rejalashtirishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari.....	200
Abdurashit Karimovich Avliyakov	
Tarbiya darslari samaradorligini oshirishda abdulla avloniy pedagogik hikmatlaridan foydalanishni metodik tashkil etish.....	204
Daliyeva Eliza Zokir qizi	
Badiiy-tarixiy meros asosida bo'lajak pedagoglarning refleksiv tafakkuri va kasbiy identifikatsiyasini rivojlantirish	207
Qodirova Mavluda Maxodir qizi	
Adabiyot darslarida lirik asarlarni vizual yondashuvlar asosida o'qitish usullari.....	210
Sobitova Mahmudaxon Shuxratbek qizi	
ESG tamoyillarini ta'lim tizimiga joriy etish orqali talabalarda ekologik, ijtimoiy va boshqaruv ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	216
Tursunova Shahzoda Baxromovna	
Социально-психологические факторы нарушения психологического здоровья в семье	219
Гулру Тургунова	
O'zini tarbiyalash (self-development) g'oyasining Ibn Sino ta'limotidagi o'rni	229
Usmanova E'zoza Zokirjonovna	
Оценка динамики физиологических показателей волейболистов 12–16 лет в предсоревновательный и соревновательный периоды	234
Умматалиева Шерзода Шерали угли	
Individual sport turlarida sportchilarning natijadorlik kompetensiyasini motivatsion omillar asosida shakllantirish.....	239
Baratov Nasriddin Karshibayevich	
O'smirlarda internetdan ortiqcha foydalanishning psixologik oqibatlarini	243
Fayziyeva Nodira Sobirovna	
Transakt analiz: shaxslararo muloqotni tahlil qilishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari	247
Nilufar Sayfidinovna Sangirova	
Inklyuziv ta'lim jarayonini boshqarish mexanizmlarini rivojlantirish (umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari misolida)	252
Abdug'aniyev Abdurauf Abdumannonovich	
O'zbek milliy kurashining tarixiy rivojlanish bosqichlari va uning yoshlar tarbiyasidagi pedagogik ahamiyati.....	257
Xomudjonova Feruza Komiljon qizi, Almardanov Xasan Asqarovich	
Belbog'li kurashning shakllanishi va rivojlanish tarixi: jismoniy tarbiya tizimidagi o'rni va metodik imkoniyatlari	261
Xomudjonova Feruza Komiljon qizi, Norqizilov Muxammadbek Sherali o'gli	

Dzyudo kurashining tarixiy evolyutsiyasi va uning ta'lim jarayonida kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida qo'llanishi	265
<i>Xomudjonova Feruza Komiljon qizi, Norqobilov Jamshid G'ulomovich</i>	
Dzyudo kurashining tarixiy evolyutsiyasi va uning ta'lim jarayonida kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida qo'llanishi	270
<i>Xomudjonova Feruza Komiljon qizi, Nurullayev Fazliddin Murodulla o'gli</i>	
Raqamli muhitda shaxs xulq-atvori dinamikasi (bolalik va o'smirlilik misolida).....	275
<i>Raimdjanov Mirkarim Tolibjon o'g'li</i>	
O'quvchilarning intellektual qobiliyatlarini oshirishning pedagogik va psixologik asoslari	278
<i>Suvanova Baxtigul Baxridinovna</i>	
Xalqaro tajriba asosida o'quvchilarda tadbirkorlik ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish mexanizmlari.....	283
<i>Azimov I. T., Mirzayeva N. I.</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda ingliz tili o'qitishda didaktik vositalardan foydalanish	288
<i>Ziyaboyeva Sevara Saydullayevna</i>	
Yuqori malakali o'rta masofaga yuguruvchilarning jismoniy rivojlanish dinamikasi	292
<i>Nazarov Nuriddin Baxranovich</i>	
Maktab direktorining partisipativ boshqaruv faoliyatida qarorlar qabul qilish jarayonida ishtirokchilarning roli	297
<i>Jabborova Yulduzxon Hasan qizi</i>	
Tibbiyotda nizoli vaziyatlar va ularni bartaraf etish usullari.....	301
<i>Olimova Dono Shakirovna, Baxtiyorova Shahnoza Mansurbekovna</i>	
Ichki kasalliklarni tashxislashda klinik fikrlashning o'rni.....	304
<i>Tilavova Muqaddas, Hasanova Munisa, Mamatqulova Fayzo, Hakimova Xonbuvi Hakimovna</i>	
Транснациональные компании и проблема суверенитета национального государства.....	307
<i>Ф. Равшанов, Л. Сохибова</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda o'quv-biluv faoliyati motivatsiyasini rivojlantirishning pedagogik ahamiyati	311
<i>Muhammadiyeva Manzura Maratovna, Musulmonova Sabrina Akmal qizi</i>	
Texnologik ta'limda xorijiy tajriba	316
<i>Lochinbek Abdirasulov</i>	
Talabalarda ilmiy-tadqiqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	319
<i>Saffarova Mohidil Axmadovna, Mustafayeva Feruza Anvar qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ona tili darslaridagi asosiy resurslari: "ona tili" darsligi, mashq daftari, o'qituvchi kitobi ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishning muhim omili sifatida.....	324
<i>Soatova Hilola Shuhrat qizi</i>	
Harbiy vatanparvarlik tarbiyasi – zamonaviy jamiyat taraqqiyotining muhim omili sifatida.....	328
<i>R. D. Mustayev, H. F. Abduvositov</i>	
Русскоязычная литература Узбекистана современного периода: проблематика, поэтика и художественный анализ	332
<i>Чернова Татьяна Алексеевна</i>	
O'smirlar orasida tengdoshlar bosimi va uning psixologik ta'siri	335
<i>Toshpo'latova O'giloy Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda iste'mol madaniyatini shakllantirish jarayonida targeting yondashuvining pedagogik nazariy asoslari	339
<i>D. G. Umnov</i>	
Ona tili darslarini ikkinchi til tamoyillari asosida tashkil etish masalalari.....	344
<i>Maxkamova Guluzroxon Abdumutalibovna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida mustaqil ishlarni pedagogik jihatlardan tashkil etishning nazariy va amaliy aspektlari	347
<i>Mahkamov Mahammadjon Dadajonovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda interfaol metodlar asosida dars jarayonini takomillashtirish metodikasi	351
<i>Muhammadjonova Durdonaxon Bahromjon qizi</i>	
Tarix darslarini modellashtirishda pedagogik metodlar tasnifi va ularning samaradorligi	354
<i>Ikrom Qodirov</i>	

Hadassah hospital maktabi modelining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, pedagogik samaradorligi va uni O'zbekiston hospital maktablariga tatbiq etishning ahamiyati	357
<i>Abdullayev Aziz Habibullayevich, Ochilov Orazbek Qosim o'g'li, Alimova Dono Abbosxonovna</i>	
Davlat boshqaruvi tizimida korrupsiyaviy xavf-xatarlarni baholash va prognozlash metodologiyasi.....	361
<i>Amirxo'jayev Shukurjon Qurbonovich, Sotvoldiyev Akbarjon Umidjon o'g'li</i>	
Neyropedagogik yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarda pozitiv fikrlashni rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy va amaliy asoslari	364
<i>Babakulova Dilnoza Ramazonovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda nutqiy nuqsonlarning oldini olish va o'quvchilarning talaffuz madaniyatini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	367
<i>Baxtiyorova Nastarin Baxriddinovna, Daminova Dilbar Melimurodovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining bilim olishga qiziqishini oshirishda gamifikatsiya elementlaridan foydalanishning nazariy-metodik asoslari.....	370
<i>G'aniyeva Gulxayyo Islom qizi, Raxmatova Shaxlo Mansurovna</i>	
Ingliz tili darslarida kitobxonlik ko'nikmalarining o'ziga xosligi	373
<i>Jo'raboyeva Turg'unoy Ikromjon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida lingvokognitiv kompetentlikni rivojlantirishning didaktik tizimi.....	377
<i>Kozimova Sadoqat</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablarida tabiiy fanlar (science)ni o'qitish orqali ekologik savodxonlikni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari	380
<i>Majitov Turg'unali Anvar o'g'li</i>	
Oilaviy munosabatlarda manipulyativ muloqot indikatsiyasi: psixologik tahlil va eksperimental natijalar.....	383
<i>Nishanova Zulfizar Yashin qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak mutaxassislarining kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirishda raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalarining o'rni.....	386
<i>Nurulloyev Firuz No'monjonovich</i>	
Talabalarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning tarixiy-pedagogik asoslari (ma'rifatparvar mutafakkirlar merosi misolida).....	390
<i>Sabirov Kaxramon Bektursun o'g'li</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi 5-6 yoshli bolalarda muammoli vaziyatlarni mustaqil yechish qobiliyatini shakllantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	393
<i>Tillayeva Vasila O'ktam qizi</i>	
Kritik fikrlash kompetensiyasining pedagogik va didaktik mazmuni	398
<i>Tursunaliyev Shaxzod Sherali o'g'li</i>	
Kurashchi qizlarning texnik harakatlarini kinematik va kinetik modellashtirish	402
<i>Xomudjonova Feruza Komiljon qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'limda ishga doir muloqot asoslari fanini o'qitish orqali talabalarning og'zaki fikrlash va nutq faoliyatini rivojlantirish	406
<i>Yuldasheva Dilnoza Bekmurodovna</i>	
Роль онлайн-платформ и образовательных сервисов в формировании ответственности студентов.....	409
<i>Гуламов Жасур Баходирович</i>	
Изучение изменений полярного переключения негативных и позитивных эмоций среднего воздействия в процессе развития/реабилитации механизмов эмпатии	413
<i>Ягудин Дмитрий Рустамович</i>	
Produktiv nutq ko'nikmalari orqali nutq aktlarini o'qitish samaradorligi.....	421
<i>Sadikov Erkin Tursunovich</i>	
Проблемы формирования письменной коммуникативной компетенции у студентов выпускных курсов высших учебных заведений	424
<i>Раджабова Зебинисо Анваровна</i>	
Pedagogika sohasida yangi ilmiy yo'nalish – pedagogik innovatsiya.....	427
<i>M.U. Raxmanova</i>	

Muammoli o'qitish asosida kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarning ijodiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish.....	431
<i>Giyasova Shaxnoza Abdurafikovna</i>	
9–10 yoshli o'quvchilar orasidagi nizolarni korreksion yondashuv bilan boshqarish	435
<i>Qulmatov Sindorqul Ibragimovich, Yarbekova Yulduz Bahromjon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda raqamli mediakompetentlikni rivojlantirish	439
<i>Mo'minova Madina, Mamasodiqova Saida</i>	
Разработка приложения для визуализации и анализа решения задач линейного программирования.....	442
<i>Маматов Ислонбек Ильесович, Буронова Муниса Баходировна</i>	
Mustaqil ta'lim topshiriqlarini integrativ modellashtirish tashkiliy-metodik muammo sifatida	448
<i>Ibroximova O'g'iloy Inomjon qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda axloqiy tarbiyani baholash va "tarbiya kundaligi"ni joriy etish metodikasi.....	451
<i>Norimboyeva Sarvinoz Abror qizi, Norimboyeva Sarvinoz Abror qizi</i>	
Talabalarda vatanparvarlik fazilatlarini rivojlantirishning nazariy-pedagogik va didaktik asoslari.....	456
<i>Xaydaraliyev Xurshid Xamidullayevich</i>	
Zamonaviy yosh oilalarda gender munosabatining o'rganilganlik holati	462
<i>Abduqayumova Gulnoza Karimjon qizi</i>	
Arifmetik progressiyani o'qitishda "progressiya konstruktori" amaliy-tadqiqot metodining samaradorligi....	466
<i>Abdurahmonova Zamira Raxmatullayevna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarining kasbiy kompetentligini shakllantirishning mazmuni.....	471
<i>Ashurova To'lg'anoy Ergashevna</i>	
Onlayn shaxmat platformalarining boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari tafakkuriga ta'siri	475
<i>Boboqulov Chori Urolovich</i>	
Ta'lim tizimida boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirish.....	480
<i>Kadirkulov Dilmurod Alimahamedovich</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirish mezonlari.....	485
<i>Mirsagatova Nargiza Sayfullayevna</i>	
Communicative Language Teaching in Modern Classrooms: Strengths, Limitations, and Pedagogical Implications	490
<i>Mirzaliyeva Sarvinoz</i>	
Pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasasi talabalarining fizikadan metodik faoliyatga tayyorgarligini rivojlantirish	493
<i>Murtazayev Zohid Murtazayevich</i>	
Zo'ravonlikning inson ruhiyatiga salbiy ta'siri va oqibatlari	497
<i>Mutabarxon Maxsudova</i>	
STEM ta'limi sharoitida o'quvchilarning texnik tafakkurini rivojlantirishning transdisiplinar metodik modeli	501
<i>Normuxamedov Zarif</i>	
Jadidchilar asarlarida boshlang'ich ta'limga oid pedagogik qarashlarning nazariy asoslari	507
<i>Sariboyeva Aziza G'apur qizi</i>	
Pedagogika tarixida dars samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha qarashlar va amaliyotdagi innovatsion loyihalar tahlili.....	510
<i>To'raqulova Feruza Jobir qizi</i>	
Yosh qizlarda shaxsiy mustaqillik va oilaviy mas'uliyat muvozanati	514
<i>To'xtamatova Nargiza, Boltaboyeva Marg'uba</i>	
Individual dars mashg'ulotlari orqali boksning faolligini aniqlash xususiyatlari	517
<i>Usmonov Mansur Qurbonmurotovich</i>	
Преимущества и недостатки использования виртуальных лабораторных работ по физике	522
<i>Тилова Турдихол Баратовна</i>	
Neyrolingvistik dasturlashning (NLD) nazariy va amaliy jihatlari	529
<i>Xolikova Dilobarxon Maxsitovna</i>	

Tabiiy fanlar darslarini o'qitishda muammoli texnologiyalardan foydalanish usullari	533
<i>Ochilova O'g'iloy Mardon qizi</i>	
Communicative-Pragmatic Analysis of Binary-Based Parems in English, Uzbek, and Russian Languages.....	537
<i>Jumanova Sabrina Vaydullo kizi</i>	
Kurash mashg'ulotlarida raqamli texnologiyalar qo'llanilishi.....	542
<i>Melikuziyev Azizjon Adaxamjon o'g'li</i>	
O'spirinlarda kasbiy tanlov noaniqligi sharoitida mustaqil qarorlarni rivojlantirishning psixologik xususiyatlari	546
<i>Karimova Gulxumor Shodi qizi</i>	
ChatGPT kabi til modellarining ta'lim va fan sohasiga ta'siri	550
<i>Djabbarova Xabiba Kuvandikovna</i>	
Biologiya ta'limida qo'llaniladigan masala va mashqlarning turlari, mazmuni va kreativlikni rivojlantirishdagi o'rni	554
<i>Yusupova Lobar Nizomjon qizi, Raxmatov Uchkun Ergashevich</i>	
Сравнительный анализ русской и узбекской концептосфер в контексте преподавания РКИ.....	560
<i>Рустамова Феруза Махмуджановна</i>	
Professional ta'lim muassasalari o'quvchilarining kasbiy madaniyatini kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish texnologiyalari	565
<i>Imomov Musurmon Pirnazarovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda aksiologik qadriyatlar va raqamli kompetensiyalarni uyg'un rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	572
<i>Shabbazova Dilfuza Ruzikulovna</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy ijodkorligini rivojlantirishda klaster integratsiyasi va refleksiv yondashuvning o'rni	576
<i>Shabbazova Nodira Xamzayevna</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablarida immersiv texnologiyalar imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish	579
<i>Axmedova Dilnoza Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Tasviriy san'at ta'limida kompozitsiya o'qitishning takomillashtirilgan metodik tizimi.....	581
<i>Karshiboyeva Dilafuz Boxodirovna</i>	
Bo'lajak ona tili o'qituvchilarining og'zaki va yozma nutqini rivojlantirishda refleksiv topshiriqlarning o'rni .	584
<i>Altibayeva Malika Kuvandikovna</i>	
STEAM yondashuvi asosida rivojlantiruvchi markazlarning samaradorligini oshirish yo'nalishlari.....	587
<i>O'rinova Feruza O'ljayevna, To'xtaboyeva Maftunaxon G'aniyevna</i>	
Aholi o'rtasida ommaviy sportni rivojlantirishning ilmiy-uslubiy asoslari.....	591
<i>Davulov Ozodbek Qalandarovich</i>	
Tasavvufda ma'naviy tarbiya tushunchasi va uning nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	595
<i>Satimova Sevinch Sardorbekovna</i>	
Teaching Literary and Non-Literary Forms of Speech to Young Learners.....	600
<i>Nargiza Tulyaganova</i>	
Pedagog kadrlarni innovatsion faoliyatga tayyorlashni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirishning metod va mexanizmlari	604
<i>Aziboyev Shuhrat Olimovich</i>	
Cerebral falajli bolalarda sensor, diqqat va motor funksiyalar integratsiyasining faktorli tahlili	608
<i>Karimberdiyev Azamat Axmadjon o'g'li</i>	
O'smirlik davrida emotsional intellektni namoyon bo'lishining psixologik xususiyatlari	614
<i>Djumabaeva Manzura Bagibekovna, Zoirova Laylo Alisher qizi, Umirboyeva Zaxro Dilmurod qizi</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim modellari mohiyati va ularning pedagogik tizimdagi o'rni (4K, 5E, 5I modellari misolida).....	617
<i>Raxmatov Uchkun Ergashevich, Qodirova Marjona Azamat qizi</i>	
Ayollarni iqtisodiy faollikka tayyorlashda o'quv dasturlarini loyihalash tamoyillari	624
<i>Diyarova Shaxloxon Rovshan qizi</i>	

Interfaol ta'lim metodlari asosida o'qituvchilarning kreativlik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish metodikasi: tajriba-sinov natijalari tahlili	628
<i>Abdiyeva Shodiyona Yodgor qizi</i>	
Raqamli muhitda maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyalanuvchilarining qo'shimcha ta'limini tashkil etish: tadqiqotlar sharhi	633
<i>Amanova Dilorom Faxritdin qizi</i>	
Kognitiv tilshunoslikda skript atamasi va uning voqelanish mexanizmlari	637
<i>Fayzullayev Shohrux</i>	
The Concept of Blended Learning and its Role in the Modern Educational Paradigm	641
<i>Fozilova Maxina Adashevna</i>	
Finlyandiya boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida matematika fanini o'qitish metodikasi	645
<i>G'aybulloyeva Yulduz Mexriddinovna</i>	
Xalq hunarmandchiligi bo'yicha o'quvchilarning kreativ qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	651
<i>Isoqov Shohruh Turabek o'g'li</i>	
Communicative-Pragmatic Analysis of Binary-Based Paremias in English, Uzbek, and Russian Languages	654
<i>Jumanova Sabrina Vaydullo kizi</i>	
Internet-risk profilaktikasining bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni tayyorlashdagi o'rni	659
<i>Mamatxanova Nargiza Toxirovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida inklyuziv ta'limni samarali tashkil etishning psixologik-pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	663
<i>N. Sh. Abdullayeva, F. R.Valiyeva, S. S. Raximova</i>	
Musiqiy-ritmik harakatlarning asosiy komponentlari va ularni rivojlantirishda SI imkoniyatlari	667
<i>O. A. Shodiyeva</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida kredit-modul tizimi asosida ta'limni tashkil etishning pedagogik xususiyatlari ..	672
<i>Y. R. Azzamov</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida integratsion yondashuv asosida bolalarni ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalashning pedagogik asoslari	676
<i>Yakubova Zilola Zikirovna</i>	
Aksiologik yondashuv asosida talabalarda mas'uliyatni rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	679
<i>Teshayeva Dilnoza Chori qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida bolalarni tasviriy faoliyat turlari asosida estetik tarbiyalash masalalari.	684
<i>Yuldasheva Dilshoda To'lqinovna</i>	
Профессиональная рефлексия как фактор развития научного интеллекта будущего педагога в системе педагогического образования	688
<i>Анварова Хуснора, Isoxоnova Aziza</i>	
Толерантность в мультикультурном обществе	692
<i>Бекбосынова З. К.</i>	
Методика работы над ошибками как средство повышения грамотности	696
<i>Исмаилова Мадинабону</i>	
Методы и подходы к развитию профессиональной лексической компетенции студентов военных направлений	701
<i>Хамидова Нигора Тулкуновна</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim muhiti va uning maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar rivojiga ta'siri	704
<i>Xayriddinova Parvinabonu Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalarida "botanika" fanini o'qitish samaradorligini oshirishda elektron ta'lim resurslardan foydalanish metodikasini takomillashtirish	707
<i>Nasirova Shahlo Qutbiddinovna</i>	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning intellektual va ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda media ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning o'ziga xosligi	710
<i>Mahmudjanova Ro'za Mahmudjan qizi</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	O'zbekistonda jismoniy tarbiya va ommaviy sport samaradorligining tahliliy jihatlari..... 714 Aslanova Malohat Akramovna
	Differensial yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarning moliyaviy savodxonligini rivojlantirish muhim omil sifatida..... 718 Mirzayev Akramjon O'ktamjonovich, Xokimjonova Feruza Hosiljon qizi
	Jismoniy tarbiya-sog'lomlashtirish faoliyati jarayonida oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarining sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirish 721 Ne'matova Diyora Dilshod qizi
	Sport gimnastikasining yoshlar jismoniy rivojlanishidagi o'rni va ahamiyati 725 Pirimova Nargiza Adilovna
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi (3–6 yosh) bolalarda erta ingliz tili o'rganishning psixologik va pedagogik samaradorligi..... 728 Xayrullayeva Muharramxon Davronbek qizi
	Maktabgacha ta'lim sifati va samaradorligini oshirishning strategik yo'nalishlari 733 Otahanova Manzura G'ofurovna
	Development of Intercultural Communication Competence of Future Teachers in Speaking Classes as an Important Lingvodidactic Problem: Evidence From Uzbekistan's Higher Education Context..... 736 Muhammadiyeva Halima Saidahmadovna
	Bo'lajak ona tili o'qituvchilarining og'zaki va yozma nutqini rivojlantirishda reflektiv topshiriqlarning o'rni . 749 Altibayeva Malika Kuvandikovna
	Jamiyatda huquqiy madaniyatni shakllantirish va rivojlantirishda davlat hokimiyati organlari faoliyatini takomillashtirish muammolari va istiqbollari 752 Ismailov Sarvarbek Anvarbekovich, Maxkamova Munavvarxon Alisher qizi
	Psixolog talabalarda kasbiy refleksiyaning rivojlantirishning tarbiyaviy-psixologik determinantlari: muammolar va yechimlar 757 Shukurova Nargiza Ikramovna
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida valeologik madaniyatni rivojlantirishda jismoniy tarbiyaning pedagogik salohiyati 762 Xudoyberdiyev Sh. M.
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar intellektual qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda ta'lim metodlari va vositalari..... 766 Esanbekova Fotima G'ayratjonovna
	Чеховские традиции в прозе XX века (Бунин, Платонов, Шукшин) 770 Багирова Паринисо Бобировна
	Oliy ta'limda mustaqil ishlarni tashkillashtirishda nostandart testlardan foydalanishning samarali metodlari va metodik tavsiyalar..... 775 Nurnazarova Gavharoy Baxtiyor qizi
	Umumta'lim va ixtisoslashtirilgan maktab o'quvchilarida oila obrazining kognitiv va emotsional komponentlari qiyosiy tahlili 780 Toshtemirova Nigora Ibrohimovna
	Boshlang'ich sinf "Tarbiya" darsligida Abdulla Avloniyning "Turkiy guliston yoxud axloq" asari g'oyalari integratsiyalashning pedagogik imkoniyatlari 784 Tovoshova Ozoda Akmal qizi
	Noto'liq oila farzandlarida emotsional-irodaviy sohani rivojlantirish orqali ijtimoiy deadaptatsiyani bartaraf etish..... 789 Kaxarova Ozoda Abdimominovna
	Kelajak pedagog shaxsini rivojlantirishda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining psixologik ta'siri... 793 M. B. Pulatova
	Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida inson resurslarini boshqarish tushunchasining ilmiy-nazariy tahlili 796 Maraimova Muxtabar Pulatovna
	Kredit-modul modeli asosida kreativ ta'lim muhitini yaratish omillari va imkoniyatlari..... 801 Xalkuziyeva Dilnoza Baxodirovna

Maktabgacha ta'lim pedagoglarining kasbiy faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan pedagogik texnologiya modeli	805
<i>G'aniyeva Vazira Yusufvna</i>	
Xorijiy va mahalliy tajribada prognostik madaniyatni shakllantirish yondashuvlari	809
<i>Ziyoda Urinbayeva</i>	
The Role of Tolerance in the Professional Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies	813
<i>Toshpo'latov Anvar Shokir o'g'li</i>	
O'quvchilarni milliy qadriyatlar ruhida tarbiyalashda sharq mutaffakirlari merosidan foydalanish	818
<i>Eshquvvatov To'liqinjon Eshquvvatovich, Buronova Durdona Erkin qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda interfaol metodlar orqali integrativ faoliyatlarni tashkil etish	822
<i>Kubayeva Mavluda Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim jarayonida mantiqiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari	826
<i>Mirzaqobilova Sarvinoz Aliqul qizi</i>	
Zamonaviy jamiyatda ekologik mediamadaniyatni shakllantirish masalalari	832
<i>Marziyayev Janabay Kalibayevich</i>	
Alisher Navoiyning "Mahlub ul-qulub" asari asosida o'quvchilarning axloqiy fazilatlarini shakllantirish	836
<i>Karamatova Dilfuza Sadinovna, Mahmudova Niginabonu Mizrof qizi, Ravshanova Mohinur O'tkir qizi</i>	
Pedagogik amaliyot jarayonida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy karyera loyihalash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	840
<i>Djalolova Sevara Xolmurodovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida inklyuziv ta'limni tashkil etishda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar	845
<i>G'ulomova Dildora Shoirvna</i>	
Rus tilini o'qitishda grammatik kompetensiyani kommunikativ metod yordamida shakllantirish: qoidalardan jonli muloqotga o'tish metodikasi	850
<i>Arabova Muhiba Bazarovna</i>	
Bo'lajak musiqa o'qituvchisining kasbiy kompetentligini axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari asosida takomillashtirishning pedagogik muammo va ehtiyojlari	854
<i>Axrorova Munajat Mashraf qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tanqidiy tafakkur ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning pedagogik xususiyatlari	858
<i>Azizjonova Asilabonu Alisher qizi</i>	
Ta'limda innovatsion yondashuvlarning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari (pedagogik otm misolida).....	862
<i>Begmatova Dildora Saydaliyevna</i>	
Developing the Creativity of Primary School Students Through Art-Pedagogical Methods	866
<i>Dauletmuratova Bayramgul Makhsetbay kizi</i>	
Tabiiy fanlar darslarida kreativ ta'lim muhitini shakllantirishning innovatsion texnologiyalari va ularni takomillashtirish yo'llari	871
<i>Farmanova Parvina Jamshid qizi</i>	
Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida arifmetik ko'nikmalarni mustahkamlash: zamonaviy ta'limdagi innovatsion yondashuvlar.....	875
<i>Izimbetova Amina</i>	
Matematika va o'yinlar nazariyasi: strategik qarorlarni modellashtirishda rivojlanish bosqichlari va amaliy ahamiyati.....	878
<i>Jumanazarova Shahzada</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish faoliyatini rivojlantirishning ilmiy nazariy asoslari	881
<i>Laylo Berdiqulova Erkin qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari nutqini integrativ yondashuv asosida o'stirish usullari.....	885
<i>Mamatraimova Dilshoda Chorshanbiyevna, Normengliyeva Sevinch Ulug'bek qizi</i>	
STEAM texnologiyasi vositasida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kreativlikni rivojlantirish tamoyillari	889
<i>Nazirova Guzal Malikovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda maishiy ko'nikmalarni takomillashtirishning ilmiy nazariy asoslari.....	893
<i>Saydaliyeva Gavhar Burxon qizi</i>	

Fizika fanini o'qitishda formativ baholash asosida o'quvchilarning tanqidiy fikrlash kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish	896
Sobirov Avazbek Anvarovich	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ayrim emotsional holatlar (injiqlik va emotsional reaktivlik)ni boshqarish.....	903
Sultonova Nurxon Anvarovna	
Teatr pedagogikasi asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning ijodiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish modeli va metodlari	907
Tolipova Shohista Quadrat qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida emotsional intellektni rivojlantirishda didaktik o'yinlarning roli	911
Turg'unova Gulzoda Botir qizi	
Farzand tarbiyasida onaning psixologik va axloqiy ta'sirining amaliy jihatlari	916
Tuxtaboyeva Durdonaxon Tulkunovna	
Ontogenezning turli bosqichlarida shaxsning axloqiy rivojlanish xususiyatlari	919
Umaraliyev Muzaffarjon Muhammadjon o'g'li	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'zlashtirishini metakognitiv monitoring qilish va baholashning nazariy-metodik asoslari	923
Xalikova Zaxro Mirshadmanovna	
Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining psixologiyada qo'llanilishi	927
Yoqubova Gulhayo Erkin qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	931
Bilolov Inomjon O'ktamovich	
Karatening kelib chiqish tarixi	934
Isayev Saidasliddinxon Islom o'g'li	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kreativ faollikni shakllantirishga doir usul va vositalar	937
Nishonova Kamola Shokirjon qizi, Mamadjonova Hayotxon Abdulolim qizi	
Родительские установки и развитие личности	941
Кодирова Нилуфар Абдусаттор кизи	

THE ROLE OF TOLERANCE IN THE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Abstract: An in-depth analysis is presented of the role and significance of tolerance principles in the activities of internal affairs bodies. In the context of globalization and increasing social diversity, ensuring harmony among various social, ethnic, religious, and cultural groups requires law enforcement officers—particularly prevention inspectors—to apply tolerance as a key psychological and ethical value. The conceptual foundations of tolerance, its socio-psychological nature, and its reflection in international legal norms and the national legislation of Uzbekistan are examined. Mechanisms for implementing tolerance are analyzed through impartiality, intercultural communication, and adherence to the principles of social justice in preventive work with diverse social groups.

Key words: internal affairs bodies, tolerance, prevention inspector, socio-psychological factors, empathy, communicative competence, legal culture, intercultural communication.

Annotatsiya: Ichki ishlar organlari faoliyatida bag'rikenglik tamoyillarining o'rni va ahamiyati chuqur tahlil qilinadi. Globallashuv va ijtimoiy tafovutlar kuchayib borayotgan sharoitda turli ijtimoiy, etnik, diniy va madaniy qatlamlar o'rtasida hamjihatlikni ta'minlash huquqni muhofaza qiluvchi organlar, xususan, profilaktika inspektorlaridan bag'rikenglikni muhim psixologik va axloqiy mezon sifatida qo'llashni talab etadi. Bag'rikenglikning konseptual asoslari, ijtimoiy-psixologik mohiyati, xalqaro huquqiy normalar hamda O'zbekiston qonunchiligidagi ifodasi yoritiladi. Profilaktik faoliyatda turli ijtimoiy guruhlar bilan ishlash jarayonida xolislik, madaniyatlararo muloqot va ijtimoiy adolat tamoyillariga amal qilish orqali bag'rikenglikni amalga oshirish mexanizmlari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ichki ishlar organlari, bag'rikenglik, profilaktika inspektori, ijtimoiy-psixologik omillar, empatiya, kommunikativ kompetensiya, huquqiy madaniyat, madaniyatlararo muloqot.

Аннотация: Представлен всесторонний анализ роли и значения принципов толерантности в деятельности органов внутренних дел. В условиях глобализации и возрастающего социального разнообразия обеспечение согласия между различными социальными, этническими, религиозными и культурными группами требует от сотрудников правоохранительных органов, особенно инспекторов профилактики, применения толерантности как важного психологического и нравственного критерия. Раскрываются концептуальные основы толерантности, её социально-психологическая сущность, а также её отражение в международных правовых нормах и законодательстве Узбекистана. Анализируются механизмы реализации толерантности через беспристрастность, межкультурную коммуникацию и соблюдение принципов социальной справедливости в профилактической деятельности.

Ключевые слова: органы внутренних дел, толерантность, инспектор профилактики, социально-психологические факторы, эмпатия, коммуникативная компетентность, правовая культура, межкультурная коммуникация.

INTRODUCTION

In today's process of globalization, socio-political, cultural, and ideological differences emerging in society are leading to increasingly complex relationships among various social groups. In particular, the ability of law enforcement agencies—especially internal affairs bodies that work directly with the public—to engage in effective intercultural communication with citizens has become an important strategic task. In this context, an approach based on the principles of tolerance serves as a key psychological and ethical factor in ensuring social stability and fostering an environment of mutual trust.

Within the activities of internal affairs bodies, the role of prevention inspectors is of particular importance, as they are in direct contact with families, youth, and socially vulnerable groups. In performing their professional duties, tolerance, empathy, cultural sensitivity, and communicative competence are considered essential requirements. This article examines the essence of tolerance principles within the internal affairs system, their

legal, psychological, and social foundations, as well as current issues related to the practical implementation of these principles.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The role of tolerance principles in the activities of internal affairs bodies is considered one of the important directions of modern socio-psychological and legal research. Studies conducted in this field, both foreign and domestic, cover key aspects such as intercultural communication, empathy, communicative competence, and public trust within the internal affairs system. In global scholarship, the concept of tolerance is interpreted as a multifaceted social phenomenon. UNESCO (1995) defines tolerance as “respect for and acceptance of the right of others to think and live differently.” G. Allport (1954), in his work *The Nature of Prejudice*, discusses the role of tolerance in combating stereotypes in social consciousness. According to him, an impartial attitude of police and internal affairs officers can be a decisive factor in preventing social conflicts.

Bandura (1986), within the framework of social learning theory, associates employees' tolerant attitudes toward the social environment with personal experience and adaptation to external changes. U. Bronfenbrenner (1979), in his ecological systems theory, demonstrates the development of tolerance through the interaction of internal systems such as family, school, and legal institutions.

From international practice, methods of implementing tolerance in law enforcement activities have been studied in the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, and Scandinavian countries. For example, within the framework of the “Procedural Justice” model (Tyler, 2003), reforms carried out by the U.S. police emphasize fairness, respect, transparency, and trust-based relations with citizens as key indicators of tolerance.

In Uzbek scientific literature, the concept of tolerance has mainly been studied within the contexts of spirituality, education, civil society, and legal culture. N. Komilov (2002) recognizes tolerance as a human virtue grounded in moral values and interprets it as a foundation of social stability. N. N. Azizkhojaeva (2010) highlights the impact of a tolerance-based approach in pedagogical communication on the effectiveness of education.

Q. Abdurakhmonov (2006), in his work *Social Psychology of Family Relations*, substantiates that tolerance is an important psychological factor in resolving family conflicts and problems. At the same time, G. G. Abdulvaeva (2014) reveals the interconnection between family and societal tolerance in youth upbringing.

Although R. Shamsiyev (2014) and M. Alimov (2016) analyzed cultural and legal approaches to crime prevention within internal affairs bodies, they paid less attention to the practical manifestations of tolerance, empathy, and communication. Therefore, there is a need for deeper psychological analyses and the study of mechanisms for developing tolerance in a broader social context.

While many scientific sources describe tolerance as a general social value, its application to specific professional activities within the internal affairs system remains insufficiently developed. In particular, there is a lack of systematic research focusing on the psychological preparedness of prevention inspectors, their communication culture, and their tolerance-based approaches in working with citizens. International literature considers tolerance as an essential ethical competence for law enforcement personnel, whereas local literature tends to approach it more from an educational and moral perspective. Conducting in-depth analytical and empirical studies on this topic would serve as an important foundation for improving the effectiveness of internal affairs bodies.

Tolerance is not only a readiness for compromise or the ability to endure differing opinions but also involves active empathetic listening, understanding social roles, and establishing positive interpersonal relationships. The concept of “unconditional positive regard,” proposed by American psychologist Carl Rogers, is regarded as a foundation of interpersonal tolerance. This approach requires internal affairs officers to build relationships with citizens based on respect, attentive listening, and empathy.

Additionally, according to the emotional theory developed by S. Schachter and J. Singer (1962), correctly identifying and evaluating individuals' emotional states leads to tolerance-based decision-making. This is particularly relevant for internal affairs officers who operate in stressful situations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article provides an in-depth analysis of the role of tolerance principles in the activities of internal affairs bodies, their socio-psychological and legal foundations, as well as key aspects of their practical implementation. The central idea of the study is that tolerance should not only be regarded as a social value but also elevated to the level of a necessary professional competence for employees of the internal affairs system. In particular, the direct interaction of prevention inspectors with the population requires them to adopt a conciliatory, empathetic, and culturally sensitive approach in addressing various social, cultural, and psychological issues.

First, the article examines the psychological and social essence of the concept of tolerance based on the theories of scholars such as Carl Rogers, Gordon Allport, and Erich Fromm. In addition, the legal framework of this principle is outlined with reference to key documents, including the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law “On Internal Affairs Bodies,” and the “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026.”

The analysis of international experience highlights that special attention is given to teaching tolerance culture to law enforcement officers in countries such as Canada, Germany, Norway, and the United States. For example, in the Norwegian police system, special annual training programs on intercultural communication and empathy are conducted, ensuring high effectiveness in building trust-based relationships with citizens.

In local practice, it is noted that, in Uzbekistan, preventive work is carried out through the activities of prevention inspectors with families, youth, and socially at-risk individuals. From this perspective, the development of tolerance, empathy, and communicative competencies within their professional training remains a pressing issue. The article pays particular attention to scientific research methods. Conclusions are drawn based on data obtained through methods such as analysis and synthesis, comparison, content analysis, psychodiagnostics, and sociological surveys. In particular, a survey was conducted among 45 internal affairs employees and 100 citizens to study their attitudes toward tolerance principles. Additionally, the level of tolerance among employees was assessed using the “Tolerance Diagnostics” methodology.

The study also reflects the use of digital technologies. Specifically, the survey was conducted via the Google Forms platform, and the collected data were statistically analyzed using SPSS software. During the analysis, the chi-square (χ^2) test and correlation coefficients were used to determine the levels of association. Furthermore, digital monitoring and facial expression recognition technologies (face-reading) were applied to study employees’ communicative behavior within internal affairs bodies.

The main findings of the study are as follows:

1. Tolerance-based approaches exist among internal affairs employees; however, they require systematic and continuous development.
2. Employees with higher levels of tolerance demonstrate significantly greater service effectiveness and higher levels of mutual trust with citizens.
3. 65% of respondents consider tolerance to be a core element of professional training in internal affairs bodies.
4. There is potential to adapt international approaches within local practice; however, cultural context and social differences must be taken into account.

Overall, this article demonstrates the relevance of tolerance principles at the current stage of development of the internal affairs system. Tolerance is an integral component of humanity, legal culture, and professional ethics. A deep understanding and effective implementation of this principle in the activities of internal affairs employees contribute to strengthening the foundations of civil society.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This section presents the findings of a study on the importance and practical application of tolerance principles in the activities of internal affairs bodies. A total of 145 respondents participated in the study, including 45 internal affairs employees and 100 citizens. Based on the results of surveys and psychological tests, 78% of employees and 65% of citizens consider tolerance to be important in internal affairs activities. This confirms that tolerance is a key factor in fostering social trust and ensuring effective communication within internal affairs institutions.

According to the “Tolerance Diagnostics” method, 36% of employees were assessed as having a high level of tolerance, while 42% expressed readiness for intercultural communication. Statistical analysis conducted using the χ^2 (chi-square) test in SPSS revealed a positive correlation of up to 70% between the level of tolerance and service effectiveness. In addition, the average level of citizens’ trust in employees was 58%, which is directly related to the communicative competence of the staff.

Digital technologies such as Google Forms, SPSS statistical analysis tools, and monitoring systems were widely used in the study. Overall, the results indicate the need to strengthen tolerance-based approaches in the activities of internal affairs bodies, improve service quality, and establish effective communication with citizens. This, in turn, serves as an important factor in enhancing social stability and legal culture.

Reliability and Scientific Validity of the Research Results. To ensure the reliability and scientific validity of the research findings, several statistical and psychometric approaches were applied. The study involved

145 respondents (including 45 internal affairs employees and 100 citizens), which ensured the adequacy of the sample size. According to the methodology of psychological research, a sample size of $n > 100$ provides sufficient statistical power for generalizing the results.

The psychometric methods used in the study (such as the “Tolerance Level Diagnostics” and the “Communicative Competence Test”) were pre-adapted and evaluated in terms of reliability using the Cronbach’s alpha (α) coefficient. For these tests, an α value greater than 0.78 was obtained, indicating a high level of internal consistency. Furthermore, statistical analyses conducted using SPSS software—including the chi-square (χ^2) test, t-test, and Pearson correlation—confirmed the statistical significance of the results ($p < 0.05$).

Comparative Analysis. Comparative analysis shows that, although internal affairs employees generally demonstrate a relatively positive attitude toward tolerance, there are still certain gaps in practical communication and intercultural interaction. The fact that only 22% of employees possess a high level of communicative competence corresponds with 19% dissatisfaction among citizens.

The data obtained within the study were subjected to in-depth statistical analysis. The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.63$) indicates a moderate positive relationship. Based on the chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 9.47$, $p < 0.01$), a statistically significant relationship was identified between employees’ level of tolerance and service effectiveness. The Student’s t-test confirmed a significant difference between those prepared and unprepared for communication ($t = 2.73$, $p < 0.05$).

The average level of tolerance was 3.68 (on a 5-point scale), the average level of trust was 3.52, and the standard deviation was 0.74, indicating a balanced distribution of the results. Based on these findings, it is emphasized that practical recommendations should be developed to strengthen tolerance-based approaches within the internal affairs system.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the conducted research demonstrate that the role of tolerance principles in the activities of internal affairs bodies is of critical importance. In particular, intercultural communication, patience, respect, and fairness in the interactions of prevention inspectors with citizens contribute not only to strengthening law and order but also to ensuring social stability. The study shows that higher levels of tolerance and communicative competence among employees lead to increased public trust and improved effectiveness of preventive measures.

The findings, based on statistical and psychological methods, indicate that employees who adhere to tolerance principles tend to adopt constructive positions in communication with citizens, which helps prevent negative social situations. However, certain shortcomings in communicative and tolerance capacities among some employees were also identified. This necessitates a systematic approach, continuous professional development, and the introduction of modern psychological practices.

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Specialized training for employees:** introduce targeted training programs for internal affairs employees, especially prevention inspectors, focusing on tolerance, intercultural communication, stress management, and empathy skills.
2. **Evaluation system for tolerance indicators:** develop and implement performance evaluation indicators that include tolerance and communication culture within internal affairs bodies.
3. **Implementation of digital technologies:** establish digital analytical platforms (such as mobile applications, surveys, and analytical tools) to monitor and analyze communication between citizens and employees.
4. **Strengthening psychological services:** increase the number of psychologists in each regional internal affairs department and integrate their work closely with prevention inspectors.
5. **Academic collaboration:** promote cooperation with higher education institutions to conduct research, encourage practitioners’ participation in scientific activities, and enrich the analytical and psychological knowledge base.
6. **Engagement of civil society institutions:** foster positive social attitudes among citizens through tolerance-promoting projects, seminars, training sessions, and open dialogues.
7. **Improvement of the legal framework:** develop regulatory documents governing communication culture and tolerance-based practices among internal affairs employees.

Overall, the implementation of these recommendations will contribute to enhancing the effectiveness of internal affairs bodies, strengthening public trust, and promoting social stability and legal culture.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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